

SYNERGY ASSESSMENT OF HYBRID REINFORCEMENTS IN CONCRETE

Sabrina VANTADORI*, Andrea CARPINTERI*, Li-Ping GUO**,
Camilla RONCHEI*, Andrea ZANICHELLI*

*Dept. of Engineering and Architecture, University of Parma,
Parco Area delle Scienze 181/A, 43124 Parma, Italy

**School of Materials Science and Engineering, Southeast University,
211189 Nanjing, China

Corresponding Author: Sabrina Vantadori sabrina.vantadori@unipr.it

ABSTRACT

The present paper is devoted to the assessment of synergy due to the combined use of metallic and synthetic fibres in concrete matrix. Such an evaluation is performed both at first cracking stage by computing fracture toughness, and at post-peak stage by determining two toughness indexes. The results from experimental three-point bending tests on concrete specimens reinforced with copper-coated steel fibres and polypropylene fibres are employed for such computations. The novelty of this research work is that the Mixed Mode loading effect occurring at crack tip is taken into account when computing fracture toughness. Plain concrete specimens and specimens reinforced with only one type of fibres are experimentally and analytically examined for comparison.

KEYWORDS: concrete, fibres, fracture toughness, hybrid reinforcement, synergy, toughness index

NOMENCLATURE

\underline{a}	effective critical crack length
a_0	notch length
a_1, a_2	kinked crack length
B	specimen width
C_i	initial linear elastic compliance
C_u	unloading linear elastic compliance
E	elastic modulus
I_t	toughness index
\bar{I}_t	relative toughness index
$K_{(I+II)C}^S$	Mixed Mode critical stress-intensity factor
L	specimen length
m	multiplier
P_{\max}	peak load
S	loading span
W	specimen depth
$\alpha_0 = a_0/W$	initial notch-depth ratio
$\alpha = \underline{a}/W$	effective notch-depth ratio
θ	crack kinking angle

ACRONYMS LIST

CMOD	Crack Mouth Opening Displacement
CMOD _{peak}	Crack Mouth Opening Displacement at the first peak load
FRC	Fibre Reinforced Concrete
HFRC	Hybrid Fibre Reinforced Concrete

LEFM	Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics
MTPM	Modified Two-Parameter Model
TPM	Two-Parameter Model

1. INTRODUCTION

During last decades, fibres have been extensively used as reinforcement of cementitious matrices to improve their low tensile strength and weak cracking resistance. As a matter of fact, the fibres lying across the crack faces reduce the tensile displacements, improving the resistance to crack propagation (this effect is named *crack bridging mechanism*) [1,2]. Note that resistance to crack propagation in plain concrete is due to aggregate particles that, extending from one of the crack face, interlock with the opposite face (*aggregate interlocking mechanism*) reducing the shear displacements [3,4].

Fibres made of steel, glass, carbon and synthetic fibres are commonly adopted for concrete reinforcement. An interesting review on the above different types of fibres and the main application fields of fiber reinforced concretes (FRCs) has been published by Brandt [5]. Recently, cellulosic [6], mineral [7] and recycled [8,9] fibres have been widely employed as alternatives to conventional steel reinforcement of concrete.

Although almost all the commercially used FRCs involve only one type of fibres, innovative reinforcements (named hybrid reinforcements) combining together two or more types of fibres are getting more and more common in many practical applications such as

pavement design, structural repairs, and offshore constructions [10-12]. It is widely accepted by the scientific community that the use of two or more types of fibres in the so-called Hybrid Fibre Reinforcement Concretes (HFRCs) may potentially improve the overall concrete performance [13,14]. As a matter of fact, the behaviour of a hybrid composite is a weighted sum of the properties of its components, with a favourable balance between advantages and disadvantages. Such a phenomenon is usually termed as synergy.

In the present paper, the assessment of synergy due to the combined use of copper-coated steel fibres and polypropylene fibres in concrete matrix is performed. Such an evaluation is carried out both at first cracking stage by computing fracture toughness through the Modified Two-Parameter Model (MTPM) and at post-peak stage by determining two toughness indexes. The novelty of this method is that the Mixed Mode loading effect occurring at crack tip is taken into account when computing fracture toughness.

The input data needed for such calculations are obtained from an experimental campaign on notched HFRC specimens under three-point bending up to failure. Further, plain concrete specimens and specimens reinforced with only copper-coated steel fibres or only polypropylene fibres are experimentally tested and analytically examined for comparison.

2. HYBRID FIBRE REINFORCED CONCRETES: BRIEF STATE OF THE ART

According to Banthia and Gupta [15], HFRCs can be classified into three groups depending on the mechanism type developed by the fibres:

(i) mechanism based on fibre constitutive response: stronger and stiffer fibres improve the first crack strength and therefore the ultimate strength of concrete by means of the micro-crack bridging, while more flexible and ductile fibres improve fracture toughness in the post-cracking zone by means of the macro-crack bridging;

(ii) mechanism based on fibre sizes: smaller fibres provide the bridging mechanism across micro-cracks and improve the first crack strength, while bigger fibres provide the bridging mechanism across macro-cracks and improve fracture toughness;

(iii) mechanism based on fibre function: one type of fibres improves strength or toughness of the hardened concrete, while another type of fibres improves the fresh or early-stage properties of concrete, such as workability and shrinkage.

By examining the state of the art, it can be realized that a great effort has been done by several researchers in order to evaluate mechanical properties and fracture behaviour of HFRCs [16-20].

By focusing attention on the fracture behaviour of HFRCs, many studies have been carried out to analyse the bridging effect produced by fibre combination on fracture toughness. For instance, Hazmi and co-workers [21] have investigated the fracture resistance of both plain concrete specimens and HFRC (reinforced with steel and polypropylene fibres) specimens. In more detail, the fibre bridging

effect has been examined by considering edge-notched specimens under three-point bending and fracture toughness values computed according to the Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) theory. On the basis of such experimental and theoretical results, the best performance in terms of compressive strength, tensile strength, and fracture toughness has been found for the HFRC specimens.

Although the LEFM theory has extensively been used to analyse the fracture behaviour of concrete during last decades, it is well-known that a significant size effect is noticed when fracture toughness is evaluated from notched specimens through the conventional LEFM. Such a size effect is due to the presence of a zone ahead of the stress-free crack tip, characterised by nonlinear crack growth (named fracture process zone).

Several nonlinear fracture models have been proposed. The Two-Parameter Model (TPM), originally proposed by Jenq and Shah [22], can be considered one of the most powerful engineering tool suitable for determining fracture toughness of concrete. In order to take into account the nonlinear crack growth prior to the peak load, the above Authors have suggested to characterise the fracture properties of concrete by means of two material fracture parameters: the critical stress intensity factor and the critical crack tip opening displacement. Such fracture parameters are evaluated on the basis of experimental results related to three-point bending tests performed on notched specimens. The method is also implemented in RILEM recommendations, for both plain [23-25] and fibre reinforced concrete [26].

Turning back to HFRCs, the TPM has been employed to compute the fracture toughness of such concretes. For instance, Deng and Li [27] have examined the fracture behaviour of both plain concrete specimens and concrete specimens reinforced with steel and/or synthetic fibres (considering different fibre percentages) by means of the TPM. In particular, three-point bending tests on notched specimens have been performed to evaluate both the fracture toughness and the fracture energy, according to the RILEM recommendation [23]. The results clearly show that combining together both steel and synthetic fibres improves the fracture properties with respect to those of concrete specimens reinforced with one single type of fibres.

One of the main drawback related to the TPM is that such a model is based on the assumption that cracks propagate under pure Mode I loading, even if it is well-known that cracks in brittle materials (such as concrete and rocks) may deflect during the fracture extension, as has been experimentally observed in Refs [28-30].

In such a context, some of the present authors have proposed a novel model named the Modified Two-Parameter Model (MTPM), which is able to take into account the possible crack deflection (kinked crack) during the stable crack propagation, even in the case of far-field Mode I loading [31-33]. Such a deflection is the result of the biaxial stress state due to normal stress related to bending loading and shear stress related to the slippage between cementitious matrix, aggregates and fibres.

The validation of the MTPM has recently been performed by employing experimental data related to three-point bending tests on

bone [32], and plain concrete and fibre reinforced concrete [31,33] specimens. The obtained results prove that the novel model provides more realistic values of fracture toughness with respect to those determined by applying the original formulation of the TPM.

3. EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN: THREE-POINT BENDING TESTS

The tested specimens have a prismatic shape with the following geometric sizes: width (B) \times depth (W) \times length (L) = 15mm \times 30mm \times 160mm (**Figure 1**). A notch of length $a_0=10$ mm is made in the lower part of the middle cross-section.

Figure 1.

The specimen matrix is cementitious (42.5 CEM II/A-P). The following mixture proportions according to Ref. [34] are adopted for the concrete casting: cement: water: aggregates (by weight) =1:0.7:3.6. The mixture is characterised by a compressive strength of 30 MPa at 28 days. The aggregate grading curve is shown in **Figure 2**, with maximum aggregate size equal to 5 mm.

Figure 2.

Different types of specimens are tested:

- (i) plain concrete specimens (P);
- (ii) concrete specimens reinforced by copper-coated steel fibres (CC);

(iii) concrete specimens reinforced by polypropylene fibres (PP);
(iv) HFRC specimens with copper-coated steel and polypropylene fibres (CP).

Note that fibres are randomly distributed in concrete, with fibre content equal to 0.5% by volume (CC0.5, PP0.5 and CP0.5) or 1.0% by volume (CC1.0, PP1.0 and CP1.0). In the case of CP0.5 and CP1.0 specimens, the fibre percentage is equal to 0.25% and 0.5%, respectively, for each type of fibre.

The metallic short-fibres are produced by the NV Bekaert SA in Belgium [35]. Such fibres are manufactured from cold drawn steel wires with high strength, and subsequently coated with a layer of copper using an electrolytic process.

The micro-synthetic polypropylene fibrillated fibres are produced by LA MATASSINA GROUP in Italy [36]. The above fibres are deformed and/or irregular (fibrillated) in shape, and made of 100% pure high-density polypropylene.

The geometrical sizes, and the physical and mechanical properties of each fibre type are listed in **Table 1**.

Table 1.

The experimental tests are carried out under three-point bending with loading span S equal to 120mm (**Figure 1**), by employing the universal testing machine Instron 8862 available at the "Testing Laboratory of Materials and Structures" of the University of Parma. The tests are performed under Crack Mouth Opening Displacement (CMOD) control, employing a clip gauge at average speed equal to 0.5 mmh⁻¹.

As is shown in **Figure 3**, each specimen is monotonically loaded up to the peak load P_{max} . When such a load is achieved, the post-peak stage follows and, at a force value equal to about 95% of P_{max} , the specimen is fully unloaded. Finally, the specimen is re-loaded up to failure.

Figure 3.

From the visual inspection of the crack path in each tested specimen, it is observed that the crack starting from the notch tip generally deflects, as is shown in **Figure 4** for one specimen of each tested type. Such a deflection is the result of inhomogeneities embedded in the cementitious matrix. In particular, inhomogeneities can be represented by aggregates for plain concrete, and by aggregates and fibres for fibre-reinforced concrete. Therefore, a Mixed Mode loading occurs at the tip of the crack.

Figure 4.

4. FIRST CRACKING STAGE: FRACTURE TOUGHNESS COMPUTATION

4.1 Model description

The fracture toughness is evaluated by employing the Modified Two-Parameter Model [31-33], that follows the same philosophy of the TPM [22,23,37]. The flowchart of the model is shown in **Figure 5**, whereas its analytical formulation is detailed in Appendix A.

Figure 5.

The main steps of the model are here summarised. Firstly, the load-CMOD curve obtained from three-point bending test is plotted according to the experimental procedure described in Section 3.

Then the initial linear elastic compliance, C_i , and the compliance after unloading, C_u , are computed (see **Figure 3**).

Further, the elastic modulus E is evaluated as a function of both the initial compliance C_i and the geometrical sizes of the single edge-notched specimen (see Eqs (A1) and (A2)).

As is shown in **Figure 6**, the kinked crack branch consists of two segments, named a_1 and a_2 , and θ is the crack kinking angle.

Figure 6.

If a crack propagates under Mixed Mode loading, the effective critical crack length \underline{a} is assumed to be equal to the sum of the notch length a_0 and the projection of the kinked crack along the notch section. Such a length \underline{a} is determined (through an iterative procedure) as a function of the elastic modulus E , the unloading compliance C_u , and the geometrical sizes of the single edge-notched specimen (see Eq. (A3) or (A4)).

Finally, the critical stress-intensity factor $K_{(I+II)C}^S$ is computed by employing the measured value of the peak load P_{\max} and the computed value of \underline{a} (see Eq. (A5) or (A6)).

4.2 Results and discussion

By examining the experimental load-CMOD curves coming from the experimental campaign described in Section 3, it can be observed that the use of fibres generally improves the softening behaviour in comparison with that related to plain concrete specimens. For instance, as far as the load-CMOD curves for both plain concrete (P specimens, **Figure 7(a)**) and HFRC with fibre content equal to 1.0% by volume (CP1.0 specimens, **Figure 7(b)**) are concerned, a significant load-bearing capability increase in the post-peak behaviour can be noticed, even in the case of large values of CMOD. Such an improvement is mainly related to the fibre-bridging, which consists in the transmission of additional tensile stresses caused by the fibres across the crack surfaces.

Figure 7.

The results obtained are listed in **Table 2** for each tested specimen. In more detail, the measured values of notch length a_0 and peak load P_{\max} , and the results determined in terms of elastic modulus E , critical stress-intensity factor $K_{(I+II)C}^S$, crack kinking angle θ , and effective critical crack length a are reported.

Table 2.

It can be remarked that the best performance in terms of fracture toughness is achieved when 0.5% of copper-coated steel fibres are used, with a critical stress-intensity factor value about four times greater than the corresponding value for plain concrete.

An increase of the content of such a fibre type does not produce, instead, a beneficial effect on fracture toughness, being the critical stress-intensity factor only about two times greater than the corresponding value for plain concrete. The above decrease of the positive effect depends on air incorporated during the mixing phase, that increases with the amount of fibres [38].

The presence of synthetic fibres for both the used percentages by volume has a negligible effect on the critical stress-intensity factor value. The detrimental effect of air is not observed in such a case, since such fibres are fibrillated.

The synergy related to the combined use of steel and synthetic fibres is observed with respect to plain concrete and concrete reinforced with synthetic fibres. The critical stress-intensity factor value increases of about 17% by increasing the percentage of fibres, and the detrimental effect of air is not observed in this case.

5. POST-PEAK STAGE: TOUGHNESS COMPUTATION

5.1 Procedure description

Following an approach similar to that reported in the works by Gopalaratnam et al. [38] and Jamet et al. [39], a toughness index based on the measure of the area under the experimental load-CMOD curve is hereafter proposed in order to better understand the effect of both fibre type and fibre volume fraction on the fracture behaviour of concrete. More precisely, the experimental area under the load-CMOD curve reflects the energy absorption capability of

material, and can directly be correlated to the material ductility and fundamental fracture parameters.

In the technical literature, the toughness indexes are usually referred to the area under the load-deflection curve. For instance, according to the ASTM C1018 [40], the toughness index of unnotched FRC specimens is defined as the ratio between the area under the load-deflection curve up to a prescribed deflection and the area under the same curve up to the first crack deflection. In particular, the prescribed deflections are regarded as multiples of the first crack deflection value. A similar approach has been adopted by Barr and Hasso [41] to define a fracture index for both unnotched and notched FRC specimens.

It can be highlighted that the above indexes depend on the deflection value at the first crack load, which is difficult to be reliably evaluated from the experimental load-deflection curve. In particular, the first crack load is assumed to be equal to the load for which the load-deflection curve starts to deviate from the linearity and, consequently, the measure of such a load is rather subjective since it is usually done graphically.

In order to overcome such a drawback, Bryans et al. [42] have recently proposed a toughness index based on the load-CMOD area until the first peak of a notched specimen is attained. As a matter of fact, the CMOD value corresponding to the first peak load, $CMOD_{peak}$, is determined in a simpler and more objective way than the first crack value, and corresponds to the end of the cementitious matrix dominant response.

Analogously, a toughness index I_t is here defined as the ratio between the area under the load-CMOD curve up to a prescribed multiple, $m \times \text{CMOD}_{\text{peak}}$, of the CMOD at the peak load and the area under the same curve up to $\text{CMOD}_{\text{peak}}$.

In order to provide a measure of the fibre effectiveness up to complete failure and, hence, of the loading capability related to cementitious matrix in the cracked stage, a toughness index has been proposed by the ACI Committee 544 [43], defined as the ratio between the energy absorption capability of a FRC specimen and that of its unreinforced counterpart.

Following such an approach, a relative toughness index \bar{I}_t is here computed as the difference between the areas under the load-CMOD curves for FRC specimens and plain concrete specimens, respectively, up to the same value of CMOD.

5.2 Results and discussion

The toughness index I_t is computed for all the tested specimens by considering five different multipliers of the $\text{CMOD}_{\text{peak}}$ value, that is, $m=5,10,15,20,30$. The averaged values of the index I_t are listed in **Table 3**.

Table 3.

It can be remarked that, for $m=5$, the toughness index presents a similar value for each specimen type. Moreover, by considering

the same type of fibres and the same value of m , the toughness index for fibre content equal to 1.0% is greater than that for 0.5% .

On the other hand, by analysing specimens containing the same percentage of fibres, it can be observed that CC and CP specimens absorb a larger amount of energy than PP specimens, especially in the case of high values of m . Such an effect is due to the presence of steel fibres (in the cementitious matrix), which have a greater effectiveness at large deformations than that of polypropylene fibres.

The averaged results in terms of \bar{I}_t are summarised in **Table 4** for each FRC specimen type being examined.

Table 4.

It is worth noting that, for $m=5$, the relative toughness index \bar{I}_t is equal to about zero for each specimen type, since the fracture behaviour is still mainly dominated by the cementitious matrix. By increasing the value of m , the relative toughness index increases due to the effectiveness of fibres.

Moreover, by considering the same type of fibre and the same value of m , the toughness index for fibre content equal to 1.0% is greater than that for 0.5% .

Note that the PP0.5 specimen type presents negative values of \bar{I}_t . Such a result means that polypropylene fibres have a negligible effect on the absorbed energy in the case of fibre content equal to 0.5% . In order to obtain a positive effect in terms of adsorbed

energy, it is needed to have a polypropylene fibre percentage equal to 1.0% .

5.3 Comparison with literature results

The toughness results here obtained are compared with those by Caggiano et al. [44], briefly summarised hereafter. The specimens tested by the Authors had a prismatic shape (150 x 150 x 600 mm). A notch was made in the lower part of the middle cross-section, according to UNI 11039-2 [45].

The specimen matrix was cementitious (Cement 42.5). The following mixture proportions were adopted for the concrete casting: cement: water: aggregates (by weight) =1 : 0.5 : 3.8. Steel and polypropylene fibres were randomly distributed in concrete, with fibre content equal to 0.75% by volume and different proportions of such fibres in the mixture. The aspect ratio of steel and polypropylene fibres was equal to 60 and 375, respectively.

The experimental tests were carried out under four-point bending, with loading span S equal to 450mm. The tests were performed under Crack Mouth Opening Displacement (CMOD) control, at average speed equal to 0.3 mmh⁻¹.

By comparing the results by Caggiano et al. with those presented in Sub-Sections 4.2, 5.1 and 5.2, the following common trends can be highlighted:

(a) The typical failure mode of fibre-reinforced specimens is due to Mixed Mode loading occurring at crack tip;

(b) The scatter between experimental results is significantly reduced in specimens with higher content of polypropylene fibres (see **Figure 8**). As a matter of fact, a more regular distribution of polypropylene fibres is observed throughout the fracture surfaces of all tested specimens with respect to the generally non-regular ones observed in the case of steel fibres;

(c) In the post-peak stage, the polypropylene fibres tend to lose their action highlighting a crack-softening behaviour due to debonding and/or failure (see **Figure 8(c)**, and **(f)**), whereas steel fibres offer a bridging effect which results in a quite constant load-bearing capacity (see **Figure 8(b)**, and **(e)**)

Figure 8.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, the synergy due to the combined use of different fibre types embedded in the concrete matrix has been assessed. Such an evaluation has been carried out according to different approaches, in terms of both fracture toughness and toughness indexes. The novelty of such an evaluation is that Mixed Mode loading effect occurring at the tip of the crack has been taken into account in fracture toughness computation.

Experimental three-point bending tests on both plain concrete specimens and concrete specimens reinforced with copper-coated steel fibres and/or polypropylene fibres have been performed by examining two different percentages of fibre content: 0.5% and 1.0% by volume.

The analysis has highlighted that randomly-distributed fibres are able to increase the concrete resistance to fracture or the fracture toughness. The best performance in terms of fracture toughness is observed when only copper-coated steel fibres are employed.

The concrete behaviour in terms of absorbed energy, measured by employing toughness indexes, is improved by adding fibres, especially for concrete reinforced with copper-coated steel fibres and polypropylene fibres (HFRC). By increasing the percentage of fibres in the cementitious matrix, an improvement in terms of concrete fracture behaviour can be observed in the case of polypropylene fibres and HFRC, while a counter-trend can be noticed in the case of copper-coated steel fibres.

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support provided by the Italian Ministry for University and Technological and Scientific Research (MIUR), Research Grant PRIN 2015 No. 2015JW9NJT on "Advanced mechanical modeling of new materials and structures for the solution of 2020 Horizon challenges". Moreover, the authors gratefully acknowledge Nicem s.r.l. and Sicep Pinazzi for the supply of the materials employed in the production of concrete specimens.

APPENDIX A.

According to the original formulation of the TPM for plain concrete [22], the elastic modulus is determined as a function of the initial compliance C_i (Figure 3):

$$E = \frac{6S a_0 V(\alpha_0)}{C_i W^2 B} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where S is the loading span, W and B are depth and width of the specimen, respectively, and a_0 is the notch length (Figure 1). Moreover, the geometrical parameter $V(\alpha_0)$ is given by [46]:

$$V(\alpha_0) = 0.76 - 2.28\alpha_0 + 3.87\alpha_0^2 - 2.04\alpha_0^3 + \frac{0.66}{(1-\alpha_0)^2} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

being $\alpha_0 = a_0/W$ the notch depth ratio.

Under Mixed Mode loading, the effective critical crack length, $\underline{a} = a_0 + (a_1 + a_2)\cos\theta$ (Figure 6), is obtained from the following equation through an iterative procedure:

$$E = \frac{6S}{C_u W^2 B} \left\{ a_0 V\left(\frac{a_0}{W}\right) + \left[\cos^6 \frac{\theta}{2} + \sin^2 \frac{\theta}{2} \cos^4 \frac{\theta}{2} \right] \left[(a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta) V\left(\frac{a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta}{W}\right) - a_0 V\left(\frac{a_0}{W}\right) \right] + \left[\cos^3 \theta + \sin^2 \theta \cos\theta \right] \left[(a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta + a_2 \cos\theta) V\left(\frac{a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta + a_2 \cos\theta}{W}\right) - (a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta) V\left(\frac{a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta}{W}\right) \right] \right\} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where C_u is the unloading compliance, $a_1 = 0.3a_0$ and a_2 are the two segments of the kinked crack path, and θ is the crack kinking angle. Moreover, the geometrical parameter $V(\alpha)$ is deduced from Eq.(A.2) by replacing α_0 with $\alpha = \underline{a}/W$.

Note that, if the value of a_2 obtained from Eq.(A.3) is negative, it means that the effective crack length is $\underline{a} = a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta$ with

$a_1 < 0.3a_0$. In this case, the length a_1 is obtained from the following equation through an iterative procedure:

$$E = \frac{6S}{C_u W^2 B} \left\{ a_0 V\left(\frac{a_0}{W}\right) + \left[\cos^6 \frac{\theta}{2} + \sin^2 \frac{\theta}{2} \cos^4 \frac{\theta}{2} \right] \left[(a_0 + a_1 \cos \theta) V\left(\frac{a_0 + a_1 \cos \theta}{W}\right) - a_0 V\left(\frac{a_0}{W}\right) \right] \right\} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Finally, the critical stress-intensity factor, $K_{(I+II)C}^S$, is computed by employing the measured value of the peak load, P_{\max} , and considering a straight crack having length equal to the projected length of the effective kinked crack, a [46]. More precisely, when $a_1 = 0.3a_0$, the critical stress-intensity factor is expressed by:

$$K_{(I+II)C}^S = \frac{3P_{\max}S}{2W^2 B} \sqrt{\pi [a_0 + (a_1 + a_2) \cos \theta]} f(\alpha) \quad \alpha = \frac{a_0 + (a_1 + a_2) \cos \theta}{W} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

or, when $a_1 < 0.3a_0$, the following relationship has to be used:

$$K_{(I+II)C}^S = \frac{3P_{\max}S}{2W^2 B} \sqrt{\pi [a_0 + a_1 \cos \theta]} f(\alpha) \quad \alpha = \frac{a_0 + a_1 \cos \theta}{W} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Note that Eq.(A.3) is deduced by employing the Castigliano theorem in the manner suggested by Paris [47], being $a_1 = 0.3a_0$.

In more detail, let us consider a body loaded by both a loading force P and a pair of virtual forces F in equilibrium for any distance d (**Figure A1**). The Castigliano theorem states that the

displacement Δ_F of any force F (in its own direction) may be computed as follows [46]:

$$\Delta_F = \frac{\partial U_T}{\partial F} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where U_T is the total strain energy determined by adding the strain energy due to the applied forces without cracks and that due to the presence of cracks with constant applied forces:

$$U_T = U_{No\ Crack} + \int_0^A \frac{\partial U_T}{\partial A} dA \quad (\text{A.8})$$

being dA an increase in the cracked area A .

Figure A1.

By assuming a constant loading force P , the total energy rate G is equal to the rate of increase of U_T :

$$G = \frac{\partial U_T}{\partial A} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

and the relative displacement of crack surface, Δ_F , due to the forces F can be computed by replacing Eqs (A.8) and (A.9) in Eq. (A.7):

$$\Delta_F = \left(\frac{\partial U_T}{\partial F} \right)_{F=0} = \left(\frac{\partial U_{No\ Crack}}{\partial F} \right)_{F=0} + \int_0^A \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial F} \right)_{F=0} dA \quad (\text{A.10})$$

Now let us consider a prismatic specimen containing a kinked crack (**Figure 6**) and subjected to both three-point bending loading and a pair of virtual forces perpendicular to the crack surface.

The first term on the right-hand side of Eq. (A.10) is equal to zero, because it corresponds to the relative displacement produced by the pair of forces F (in their own direction) in an uncracked beam, whereas the second term is a function of the Stress Intensity Factors (SIF) values for each Mode of loading, related to the loading force P and the virtual forces F [48,49].

Once the integral of Eq. (A.10) is empirically solved and the value of C_u (equal to Δ_F/P) is taken into account, the elastic modulus E can be explicated, as is reported in Eq. (A.3).

References

- [1] Gopalaratnam VS, Shah SP, Batson G, Criswell M, Ramakishnan V, Wecharatana M. Fracture toughness of fiber reinforced concrete. *Mater J* 1991;88:339-353.
- [2] Khalifa ES. Analytical model for steel fiber concrete composite short-coupling beam. *Composites Part B* 2014;56:318-329.
- [3] Carpinteri A, Spagnoli A, Vantadori S, A fracture mechanics model for a composite beam with multiple reinforcements under cyclic bending. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 2004;41:5499-5515,.
- [4] Alberti MG, Enfedaque A, Gálvez JC, Agrawal V. Reliability of polyolefin fibre reinforced concrete beyond laboratory sizes and construction procedures. *Compos. Struct.* 2016;140:506-524.
- [5] Brandt AM. Fibre reinforced cement-based (FRC) composites after over 40 years of development in building and civil engineering. *Compos. Struct.* 2008;86:3-9.
- [6] Yan L, Kasal B, Huang L. A review of recent research on the use of cellulosic fibres, their fibre fabric reinforced cementitious, geo-polymer and polymer composites in civil engineering. *Composites Part B* 2016;92:94-132.
- [7] Fiore V, Scalici T, Di Bella G, Valenza A. A review on basalt fibre and its composites. *Composites Part B* 2015;74:74-94.
- [8] Mastali M, Dalvand A. The impact resistance and mechanical properties of self-compacting concrete reinforced with recycled CFRP pieces. *Composites Part B* 2016;92:360-376.
- [9] Mastali M, Dalvand A, Sattarifard A. The impact resistance and mechanical properties of the reinforced self-compacting concrete incorporating recycled CFRP fiber with different lengths and dosages. *Composites Part B* 2017;112:74-92.
- [10] Alberti MG, Enfedaque A, Gálvez JC. Fibre reinforced concrete with a combination of polyolefin and steel-hooked fibres. *Compos. Struct.* 2017;171;317-325.
- [11] Nguyen W, Trono W, Panagiotou M, Ostertag CP. Seismic response of a rocking bridge column using a precast hybrid fiber-reinforced concrete (HyFRC) tube. *Compos. Struct.* 2017;174:252-262.
- [12] Chi Y, Xu L, Yu H. Constitutive modeling of steel-polypropylene hybrid fiber reinforced concrete using a non-associated plasticity and its numerical implementation. *Compos. Struct.* 2014;111:497-509.
- [13] Qian CX, Stroeven P. Development of hybrid polypropylene-steel fibre-reinforced concrete. *Cem. Concr. Res.* 2000;30:63-69.
- [14] Abou El-Mal HSS, Sherbini AS, Sallam HEM. Mode II Fracture Toughness of Hybrid FRCs. *Int. J. Concr. Struct. Mater.* 2015;9:475-486.
- [15] Banthia N, Gupta R. Hybrid fiber reinforced concrete (HyFRC): fiber synergy in high strength matrices. *Mater. Struct.* 2004;37:707-716.
- [16] Kamlos K, Babal B, Nurnbergerova T. Hybrid fiber-reinforced concrete under repeated loading. *Nucl. Eng. Des.* 1995;156:195-200.
- [17] Mobasher B, Li CY. Mechanical properties of hybrid cement-based composites. *ACI Mater. J.* 1996;93:284-292.

- [18] Kim NW, Saeki N, Horiguchi T. Crack and strength properties of hybrid fiber reinforced concrete at early ages. *Trans. Japan Concr. Inst.* 1999;21:241-246.
- [19] Qian C, Stroeven P. Fracture properties of concrete reinforced with steel-polypropylene hybrid fibers. *Cem. Concr. Compos.* 2000;22:343-351.
- [20] Lawler JS, Zampini D, Shah SP. Permeability of cracked hybrid fiber reinforced mortar under load. *ACI Mater. J.* 2002;99:379-385.
- [21] Al Hazmi HSJ, Al Hazmi WH, Shubaili MA, Sallam HEM. Fracture energy of hybrid polypropylene-steel fiber high strength concrete. *WIT Trans. Built Environ.* 2012;124:309-318.
- [22] Jenq YS, Shah SP. Two-Parameter fracture model for concrete. *J. Eng. Mech.* 1985;111:1227-1241.
- [23] RILEM Technical Committee, 50-FMC, Determination of the fracture energy of mortar and concrete by means of three-point bend test on notched beams, proposed RILEM draft recommendations. *Mater. Struct.* 1985;18:285-290.
- [24] RILEM Technical Committee, 89-FMT, Determination of fracture parameters (K_sIC and CTOD_c) of plain concrete using three-point bend tests, proposed RILEM draft recommendations. *Mater. Struct.* 1990;23:457-460.
- [25] RILEM Technical Committee, 89-FMT, Size-effect method for determining fracture energy and process zone size of concrete, proposed RILEM draft recommendations. *Mater. Struct.* 1990;23:461-465.
- [26] RILEM Technical Committee, TDF-162, Test and design methods for steel fibre reinforced concrete sigma-epsilon-design method, proposed RILEM draft recommendations. *Mater. Struct.* 2002;35:579-582.
- [27] Deng Z, Li J. Mechanical behaviors of concrete combined with steel and synthetic macro-fibers. *Comput. Concr.* 2007;4:207-220.
- [28] Fanella D, Krajcinovic D. A micromechanical model for concrete in compression. *Engng. Fract. Mech.* 1988;29:44-66.
- [29] Basista M, Gross D. Internal variable representation of microcrack induced inelasticity in brittle materials. *Int. J. Damage Mech.* 1997;6:300-316.
- [30] Kuna-Ciskał H, Skrzypek JJ. CDM based modelling of damage and fracture mechanisms in concrete under tension and compression. *Engng. Fract. Mech.* 2004;71:681-698.
- [31] Vantadori S, Carpinteri A, Fortese G, Ronchei C, Scorza D. Mode I fracture toughness of fibre-reinforced concrete by means of a modified version of the two-parameter model. *Proc. Struct. Integr.* 2016;2:2889-2895.
- [32] Carpinteri A, Berto F, Fortese G, Ronchei C, Scorza D, Vantadori S. Modified two-parameter fracture model for bone. *Eng. Fract. Mech.* 2017;174:44-53.
- [33] Carpinteri A, Fortese G, Ronchei C, Scorza D, Vantadori S. Mode I fracture toughness of fibre reinforced concrete. *Theor. Appl. Fract. Mech.* 2017;91:66-75.

- [34] Colleparidi M, Colleparidi S, Troli R. Mix Design del Calcestruzzo. Ponzano Veneto (TV): Enco- Engineering Concrete, 2008.
- [35] <http://www.bekaert.com/> (last accessed 05/09/2017)
- [36] <http://www.lamatassina.it/> (last accessed 05/09/2017)
- [37] Karihaloo BL, Nallathambi P. Notched beam test: Mode I fracture toughness. In: Shah SP and Carpinteri A, editors. RILEM Report 5. Fracture Mechanics Test Methods for Concrete. London: Chapman & Hall, 1991, p. 1-86.
- [38] Gopalaratnam VS, Gettu R, Carmona S, Jamet D. Characterization of the toughness of fiber reinforced concretes using the Load-Cmod response. Fract. Mech. Concr. Struct. 1995;Proceeding:769-782.
- [39] Jamet D, Gettu R, Gopalaratnam VS, Aguado A. Toughness of fiber-reinforced high-strength concrete from notched beam tests. ACI Spec. Publ. 1995;155:23-40.
- [40] ASTM Standard, C1018, Standard Test Method for Flexural Toughness and First-Crack Strength of Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (Using Beam With Third-Point Loading). Annual Book of ASTM Standards. 2002.
- [41] Barr BIG, Hasso EBD. A study of toughness indices. Magazine of Concrete Research 1985;37:162-174.
- [42] Bryars L, Gettu R, Barr B, Ariño A. Size Effect in the Fracture of Fiber-Reinforced High-Strength Concrete. In: Bazant ZP, Bittnar Z, Jirásek M and Mazars J, editors. Fracture and Damage in Quasibrittle Structures. London: E&FN Spon, 1994, p. 319-326.
- [43] ACI Committee, 544, Measurement of properties of fiber reinforced concrete. ACI Mater. J. 1998;85:583-93.
- [44] Caggiano A, Gambarelli S, Martinelli E, Nisticò N, Pepe M, Experimental characterization of the post-cracking response in Hybrid Steel/Polypropylene Fiber-Reinforced Concrete, Construction and Building Materials 2016;125:1035-1043.
- [45] UNI11039-2 Steel Fiber Reinforced Concrete - Test Method to Determine the First Crack Strength and Ductility Indexes.
- [46] Tada H, Paris PC, Irwin GR. The Stress Analysis of Cracks Handbook. New York: ASME Press, 2000.
- [47] Paris PC. The mechanics of fracture propagation and solutions to fracture arrestor problems. Document D2-2195, Boeing Company, 1957.
- [48] Kitagawa H, Yuuki R, Ohira T. Crack-morphological aspects in fracture mechanics. Eng. Fract. Mech. 1975;7:515-529.
- [49] Cotterell B, Rice JR. Slightly curved or kinked cracks. Int. J. Fract. 1980;16:155-169.

SYNERGY ASSESSMENT OF HYBRID REINFORCEMENTS IN CONCRETE

Sabrina VANTADORI*, Andrea CARPINTERI*, Li-Ping GUO**,
Camilla RONCHEI*, Andrea ZANICHELLI*

*Dept. of Engineering and Architecture, University of Parma,
Parco Area delle Scienze 181/A, 43124 Parma, Italy

**School of Materials Science and Engineering, Southeast University,
211189 Nanjing, China

Corresponding Author:

Sabrina Vantadori sabrina.vantadori@unipr.it

LIST OF FIGURES AND TABLES CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Geometrical sizes and loading configuration of each tested concrete specimen. Lengths are in mm.

Figure 2. Aggregate grading curve.

Table 1. Geometrical sizes, physical and mechanical properties of both copper-coated steel fibres and polypropylene fibres.

Figure 3. Typical load against Crack Mouth Opening Displacement (CMOD) curve for the tested specimens.

Figure 4. Front and back side of the fractured zones, for one specimen of each tested type: (a) P; (b) CC0.5; (c) PP0.5; (d) CP0.5; (e) CC1.0; (f) PP1.0; (g) CP1.0.

Figure 5. Flowchart of the Modified Two-Parameter Model.

Figure 6. Geometrical and testing configuration of specimen according to the Modified Two-Parameter Model.

Figure 7. Typical load-CMOD curves for: (a) plain concrete specimens; (b) HFRC specimens with fibre content equal to 1.0% by volume.

Table 2. Notch length a_0 , peak load P_{\max} , elastic modulus E , critical stress-intensity factor $K_{(I+II)C}^S$, crack kinking angle θ , and effective critical crack length \underline{a} , for each tested specimen.

Table 3. Averaged values of toughness index $I_{t,m}$ for each specimen type.

Table 4. Averaged values of relative toughness index $\bar{I}_{t,m}$ for each FRC specimen type.

Figure 8. Scatter band related to the experimental load-CMOD curves for: (a) P-; (b) CC0.5-; (c) PP0.5-; (d) CP0.5-; (e) CC1.0-; (f) PP1.0; (g) CP1.0-specimens.

Figure A1. Application of the Castigliano theorem in the case of a body loaded by both a loading force P and a pair of virtual forces F in equilibrium for any distance d .

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Table 1.

FIBRE TYPE	DIAMETER	LENGTH	DENSITY	ELASTIC MODULUS	ULTIMATE STRENGTH
	[mm]	[mm]	[Kg / m ³]	[GPa]	[MPa]
Steel copper-coated	0.200	13	7.80	200.0	2500
Polypropylene	0.048	12	0.91	3.5	450-600

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Table 2.

SPECIMEN No.	a_0	P_{\max}	E	$K_{(I+II)C}^S$	θ	\underline{a}
	[mm]	[kN]	[MPa]	[MPa(m) ^{0.5}]	[°]	[mm]
P-1	9.62	182.879	18460.83	0.578	36.0	14.88
P-2	8.80	187.897	18225.01	0.552	14.0	12.26
P-3	10.44	157.120	18546.93	0.511	0.0	12.50
P-4	10.54	102.938	18681.11	0.539	13.5	16.19
CC0.5-1	8.96	366.629	20546.46	2.051	14.5	17.41
CC0.5-2	7.73	370.673	19367.86	2.047	39.5	15.71
CC0.5-3	6.63	384.389	19981.60	1.900	0.0	17.60
CC0.5-4	9.83	294.888	19239.03	2.082	14.0	19.67
CC0.5-5	8.59	362.377	20575.31	1.913	21.0	17.88
CC0.5-6	7.90	382.984	19963.38	2.00	18.0	20.52
PP0.5-1	10.95	179.505	18210.59	0.540	34.5	13.92
PP0.5-2	10.25	134.569	18348.36	0.535	14.0	15.36
PP0.5-3	9.90	192.303	18294.97	0.535	20.0	12.99
PP0.5-4	10.55	168.669	18468.92	0.540	45.0	14.25
PP0.5-5	9.66	161.012	18512.93	0.577	0.0	15.68
PP0.5-6	10.59	177.930	18676.95	0.564	11.0	16.02
CP0.5-1	9.88	125.331	15701.11	0.628	0.0	18.71
CP0.5-2	9.98	181.934	15605.19	0.671	6.0	14.21
CP0.5-3	10.67	175.524	15803.77	0.676	22.5	16.47
CP0.5-4	9.03	249.871	15943.12	0.623	0.0	11.66
CC1.0-1	10.08	315.445	18793.01	1.244	12.0	15.40
CC1.0-2	9.95	216.012	19336.21	1.007	25.5	17.14
CC1.0-3	8.44	286.996	19396.89	0.987	17.0	14.62
CC1.0-4	9.67	247.776	19437.38	1.032	10.0	14.00
CC1.0-5	9.07	255.060	18994.82	1.143	18.0	16.65
CC1.0-6	8.91	288.951	19267.03	0.972	6.00	12.61
PP1.0-1	9.38	227.350	12791.42	0.665	17.5	13.20
PP1.0-2	10.47	215.690	13178.81	0.632	16.5	10.64
PP1.0-3	11.32	194.900	12568.42	0.614	28.0	16.94
PP1.0-4	10.68	233.131	13014.16	0.600	0.0	14.13
CP1.0-1	8.58	246.794	16171.49	0.723	12.5	14.56
CP1.0-2	7.90	198.436	16414.39	0.754	0.0	14.29
CP1.0-3	8.95	195.736	16320.19	0.712	0.0	11.70
CP1.0-4	9.31	338.757	15939.66	0.801	0.0	14.61
CP1.0-5	9.25	247.258	16353.20	0.713	0.0	13.95
CP1.0-6	9.01	327.432	16113.19	0.851	13.5	10.18

Table 3.

SPECIMEN TYPE	I_t				
	$m=5$	$m=10$	$m=15$	$m=20$	$m=30$
P	5.36	8.63	10.46	13.65	-
CC0.5	5.36	9.84	13.95	17.78	24.93
PP0.5	4.90	7.38	9.07	11.41	15.88
CP0.5	5.36	9.42	13.12	16.60	23.23
CC1.0	5.65	11.25	16.72	22.02	32.90
PP1.0	5.47	9.70	13.55	17.29	24.61
CP1.0	5.49	10.15	14.65	18.95	27.21

Table 4.

SPECIMEN TYPE	\bar{I}_t			
	$m=5$	$m=10$	$m=15$	$m=20$
CC0.5	0.00	1.21	3.49	4.13
PP0.5	-0.45	-1.25	-1.39	-2.24
CP0.5	0.00	0.79	2.66	2.95
CC1.0	0.30	2.62	6.26	8.37
PP1.0	0.12	1.07	3.08	3.64
CP1.0	0.14	1.52	4.19	5.30

Figure 8.

Figure A1.